

Understanding Amniocentesis: A Review of Method and Medical Importance.

Abstract

The paper “*Understanding Amniocentesis: A Review of Method and Medical Importance*” talks about the medical interpretation of the process. It explains the pros and cons of Amniocentesis. The paper has also provided a historical overview on Amniocentesis. The study also examines whether the process is only used to diagnose genetic disorders like Down syndrome and other abnormalities like- Neural Tube Defect and Cleft Palate. Furthermore, the paper will delve into the darker aspects of Amniocentesis such as the process of sex-determination and female foeticide.

Keywords: Amniocentesis, Down syndrome, Neural Tube Defect, Genetic Disorders, Female Foeticide, Amniotic Fluid.

Introduction:

Amniocentesis is a process used to obtain a small sample of *Amniotic Fluid* that surrounds the foetus, using a needle and a syringe. Amniotic fluid is a clear yellow, pale fluid¹ which surrounds the foetus. It performs the following functions-

1. Protects the foetus from any injury and acts as a shock absorbent.
2. Provides protection against infection.²
3. Allows the baby to move freely.
4. Also maintains temperature.

It is done to check genetic and chromosomal disorders such as Down syndrome (Trisomy 21)³, Edwards’ syndrome (Trisomy 18)⁴ and Patau’s syndrome (Trisomy 13)⁵. It also helps diagnose neural tube defects (NTD).⁶ NTD’s are a group of congenital malfunctions caused by incomplete closure of the Neural Tube during embryonic development. For example: *Spina bifida* and *Anencephaly*.⁷ Apart from the above-mentioned, Amniocentesis also checks Sickle cell disease, *Thalassemia*, *Cystic fibrosis* and *Muscular dystrophy*.⁸

As of 2025, Amniocentesis also raises some medical and ethical concerns since nowadays, Amniocentesis isn't just used for treatment and diagnostic purposes but also used illegally in the following ways:

1. Determining the sex of the foetus which results in female foeticide⁹
2. Unethical genetic selection.
3. Commercial exploitation.

This paper aims to provide an overview of amniocentesis, highlighting its medical significance, historical development, and diagnostic value. At the same time, it explores the ethical and legal concerns surrounding its misuse, with particular focus on sex determination and female foeticide.

History:

Amniocentesis has been in practice for more than a century. The earliest procedures were reported by Dr. Richard Prochownick¹⁰ in 1877, Dr. von Sachs¹⁰ in the 1890s, and Dr. Karl Lamb¹⁰ in the 1930s. Initially, it was performed by abdominal needling (insertion of a needle through the abdomen) to relieve excessive amniotic fluid in complicated pregnancies.¹¹

Later, American obstetrician Dr. Fritz Fuchs¹² and Danish gastroenterologist Dr. Povl Riis¹³ were the first to report the genetic examination of amniotic fluid. This marked a turning point in the use of amniocentesis for prenatal diagnosis rather than only therapeutic purposes.

By the 1950s and 1960s, amniocentesis became more widely practiced worldwide, particularly among women at high risk of genetic disorders. It also came to be used for assessing fetal lung maturity in cases where premature delivery was suspected.

Process:

The process starts with checking the blood pressure, heart rate and the breathing rate of the patient. Ultrasound is also used to check the foetal heart rate, the position of the placenta, and to identify a safe pocket of amniotic fluid.¹⁴

A minimally painful procedure of inserting the needle into the uterus and the amniotic sac takes place. The needle, connected to the syringe, collects around 15–20 mL of amniotic fluid.

The Amniotic fluid is then sent to the laboratory for further tests while the injected area of the patient is cleaned and dressed.

Application:

Amniocentesis has various applications, few are stated below:

1. **Neural Tube Defects:** NTD's are a group of congenital malfunctions caused by incomplete closure of the Neural Tube during embryonic development. For example: *Spina bifida* and *Anencephaly*.⁷ Apart from the above-mentioned, Amniocentesis also checks Sickle cell disease, Thalassemia, Cystic fibrosis and Muscular dystrophy.⁸
2. **Foetal Lung Maturity:** In high-risk pregnancies, amniotic fluid testing determines whether the baby's lungs are developed enough for early delivery.¹⁵
3. **Genetic and Chromosomal diagnosis:**
 - a. Down syndrome (Trisomy 21): Causes intellectual disability and characteristic facial features.¹⁶
 - b. Edwards' syndrome (Trisomy 18): Severe developmental delay and fatal during infancy.¹⁷
 - c. Patau's syndrome (Trisomy 13): Severe neural and cardiac immaturities.¹⁸

There are also potential risks while performing amniocentesis.¹⁹

1. There is a risk of fetomaternal haemorrhage.¹⁹
2. There can be haematoma of maternal skin or intestinal or internal organ injuries.¹⁹
3. Amniotic fluid leakage can take place.¹⁹

Legal and Ethical Concerns:

Amniocentesis, albeit a medical procedure, has potential misuses and ethical concerns. As mentioned before, it is not only used for diagnostics and treatment purposes but can also be misused for sex determination, which sometimes leads to female feticide. Selective abortion of a female fetus after sex

determination is called female feticide. This practice occurs mainly in India due to several socio-economic and cultural factors:²⁰

1. Economic and Dowry System: Families may prefer male children to avoid the financial burden of dowry, which incentivizes the selective abortion of female fetuses.²⁰
2. Social Status: Sons are often considered responsible for continuing the family lineage and taking care of parents during old age, increasing the preference for male children.
3. Gender Roles and Cultural Norms: Traditional roles assign men as breadwinners and working members of the family and women as homemakers, reinforcing biases against female children.
4. Lack of Education and Awareness: Limited awareness about gender equality and legal consequences of female feticide perpetuates the practice.
5. Gender Discrimination: Societal preference for males over females creates systemic discrimination, leading to the misuse of prenatal diagnostic techniques.

In India, the misuse of amniocentesis for sex determination is illegal under the Pre-Conception and Pre-Natal Diagnostic Techniques (PCPNDT) Act, 1994. The Act prohibits prenatal sex determination and penalizes medical practitioners and parents involved in female foeticide.²¹

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